

A Decade of Greek Immigration and Asylum Policy (2015-2024): A Balancing Act of EU Participation, Humanitarian Obligations, and Security Concerns

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INTRODUCTION

Greece was at the forefront of the European Union's (EU) immigration and asylum policy implementation during the migration crisis of 2015–2016. Throughout this period, it is estimated that more than one million migrants and refugees traveled through Greece, moving toward other Western European countries.¹ The sheer size of this transient population—and its multifaceted political and social implications for European countries—prompted the EU to attempt to curb the influx of immigrants to Greece and, by extension, to its member states. In 2023, almost a decade later, a tragic shipwreck near Pylos claiming over 600 lives, as well as ongoing discussions by several actors and organizations regarding Greece's migrant pushbacks, has brought the country under the European spotlight once again.

Within this context, this article aims to outline key developments in Greek immigration and refugee policy over the past decade. In addition, it will provide an overview of the instrumental EU initiatives that helped Greece cope with this evolving and pressing situation. The article will discuss the establishment of the

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Emergency Support to Immigration and Accommodation (ESTIA) humanitarian assistance mechanism, which serves to better address the immediate and long-term needs of asylum seekers in the country. Furthermore, it will present the main initiatives undertaken by the EU within the scope of its 2015 Agenda on Migration. Apart from the resettlement and relocation programs, the main emphasis will be placed on the implementation of the EU's "hotspot approach" and its effects on both Greece and the aforementioned population of refugees and asylum seekers.

The third aspect that this article explores is Turkey's weaponization of migrants and refugees in Greece's Evros region during the spring of 2020. The article will specifically discuss the support granted by the EU to Greece through both symbolic gestures and tangible measures. In addition, it will cover the changing EU discourse regarding the role of Greece as a protector of EU borders.

The article will conclude by briefly addressing future challenges directly linked to migration management on the outskirts of the EU: refugee integration in the host society, the balancing of security concerns with humanitarian obligations, and the evolving political landscape regarding migration management within the EU.

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SETTING THE CONTEXT: IMMIGRANT AND REFUGEE FLOWS TOWARD GREECE SINCE 2015

During 2015–2016, Greece experienced a significant influx of migrants and refugees, primarily due to the Syrian civil war and other conflicts in the Middle East and North Africa. It is estimated that over a million immigrants and refugees crossed through the country, primarily continuing their journey to Germany but also to other European destinations like Sweden, Austria, and France.² The majority of those who traveled were from Syria, Afghanistan, and Iraq.³ This movement came to a halt in early 2016 due to two main causes: the gradual closure of borders along the Balkan route, which impeded migrants and refugees from further progressing toward European States and the 2016 EU Turkey Statement, which significantly deterred migrants and refugees crossing from Turkey to Greece.

Since late 2015, European countries have progressively closed their borders to prevent the entry of migrants and refugees.⁴ In March 2016, North Macedonia closed its land borders with Greece, effectively entrapping a population of immigrants. Shortly thereafter, the EU and Turkey signed a Common Statement to curb the flow of immigrants and refugees from Turkey to Greece.⁵

The statement aimed to stifle irregular migration from Turkey to the EU and disrupt smugglers' business models. While controversial and heavily criticized by both human rights organizations and scholars, the statement nevertheless proved effective in reducing the absolute numbers.⁶ Over 150,000 immigrants and refugees entered Greece between January and March 2016, whereas that number dropped to less than 4,000 in April and continued to decrease in the months that followed.⁷

With borders closed on both entry and exit from Greece, migrants in the country found themselves stranded. It should be noted that despite over a million individuals crossing Greece between 2015 and 2016, the vast majority had already left the country by the time the EU-Turkey Statement was signed. As such, the Greek Asylum Service estimated that there were 27,600 people on the mainland hoping to apply for asylum in the summer of 2016.⁸ A major challenge for the state was providing for the migrants' basic and immediate needs until they applied for asylum and had their applications examined.

Throughout previous decades, Greece had not established a mechanism to adequately address the needs of asylum seekers and refugees. Prior to 2011, the Greek asylum system faced significant criticism on various fronts, including the role of the police in initial decision-making, the proper transposition and implementation of EU Directives, and the elimination of the appeal procedure.⁹ Even though

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Greece went on to change a number of controversial legal provisions, limited administrative capacities and a significant discord between EU and domestic legislatures meant that these reforms lacked proper implementation and were, in essence, a checkbox formality.¹⁰ Additionally, the European Court of Human Rights and the Court of Justice of the European Union ruled in 2011 that the systemic deficiencies in the Greek asylum procedure violated the European Convention on Human Rights and EU law. Consequently, between 2011 and mid-2019, these rulings suspended transfers of asylum seekers from another Member State back to Greece under the Dublin Regulation, which dictates that the EU Member State an asylum seeker initially arrives in is responsible for processing the asylum claim.¹¹ Despite a significant overhaul of the asylum system in 2011, issues persisted in critical procedural areas, such as unlawful returns and the conditions of detention and reception.¹²

In addition to the points raised above, the vast majority of asylum applications in the country were rejected at the first instance. From 2009 to 2013, there were approximately 10,000 to 15,000 asylum applications per year, with fewer than 4 percent ultimately approved.¹³ Largely resulting from the chronic and systematic deficiencies in the asylum system that were briefly outlined in the previous paragraph and the very low numbers of recognized refugees residing in the country, Greece had not yet established a system to sufficiently provide for the needs of asylum seekers. Thus, catering to the needs of nearly 30,000 refugees and asylum seekers in early 2016 became a daunting task.¹⁴

During the same period, the country faced a severe economic crisis. At its peak in 2013, 26.5 percent of Greeks were unemployed, and according to World Bank estimates, GDP per capita had plummeted from \$32,128 in 2008 to \$17,924 in 2016.¹⁵ The repercussions of this crisis left little room for financial flexibility, making it increasingly difficult to find and allocate the necessary resources to support those seeking refuge. As a result, Greece sought assistance from the EU to address this unprecedented situation.¹⁶

The EU responded swiftly to this call for help, utilizing the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund (AMIF) as the main financial instrument. AMIF is a financial mechanism aiming, among other things, to support legal migration and immigrant integration to the EU Member States, enhance solidarity and responsibility sharing between Member States, and strengthen and develop all aspects of the common European asylum system. However, it soon became apparent that an additional mechanism was necessary to provide faster and more needs-based emergency humanitarian support. To address this, the EU established the Emergency Support Instrument (ESI).¹⁷ Interestingly, while the EU is one of the main donors of humanitarian aid internationally, this was the first time that an EU Member State required humanitarian assistance. In total, from 2015 to January 2022, Greece received €3.39 billion. The majority of these funds, amounting to €2.27 billion, came from the Asylum, Migration, and Integration Fund (AMIF), whilst an additional €668.9 million was provided through the Emergency Support Instrument (ESI), and another €450 million from the Internal Security Fund (ISF).¹⁸ The ISF is an EU Fund aiming to ensure a high level of security in the Union, foster law enforcement cooperation and enhance the management of the Union's external borders.¹⁹

ADDRESSING THE NEEDS OF ASYLUM SEEKERS AND REFUGEES

In accordance with EU regulations, specifically the Reception Conditions Direc-

tive that sets out the standards for the reception of asylum seekers, EU Member States have a legal obligation to meet the essential needs of all asylum-seekers on their soil.²⁰ During 2015–2016, however, the Greek state encountered a formidable challenge in providing for nearly 30,000 stranded individuals. Given the aforementioned lack of mechanisms and provisions, Greece primarily struggled with ensuring suitable accommodations and delivering financial aid. Regarding accommodations, two principal approaches were employed.

To increase the overall accommodation capacity, the first solution involved the establishment of temporary camps on the mainland.²¹ These open temporary accommodation and reception facilities were set up in various locations that were often geographically isolated. They included repurposed old military camps, abandoned industrial buildings, and, in some cases, old hotels.²² The number of camps consistently changed, adjusting for relevant needs. Consequently, their number was halved from 51 in 2016 to 24 in March 2022.²³ The situation in temporary accommodation facilities also changed with passing months, but a significant lack of essential living standards and infrastructures was documented by the Council of Europe Commissioner of Human Rights, especially in the early years.²⁴ Until 2020, the majority of the camps operated without an official manager. Instead, the International Organization for Migration (IOM), alongside other IGOs and NGOs, provided Site Management and Support (SMS) for their day-to-day operations, including tasks such as data management, reception, reallocation, and maintenance.²⁵

The second approach was proposed, designed, and coordinated by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). The agency promptly recognized the pressing need for reception facilities, considering that by late 2015, the Greek state had fewer than 1,200 locations available to accommodate asylum seekers and refugees.²⁶ Consequently, in late 2015, the UNHCR committed to establishing 20,000 private accommodation spaces by the end of 2016. They achieved this goal by 2018 by securing a total of 27,088 urban accommodation sites that were spread across towns, cities, and islands throughout Greece, with 60 percent situated in Athens.²⁷

This accommodation process evolved and became the housing component of ESTIA, a humanitarian assistance program established to meet the needs of asylum seekers in Greece. ESTIA was EU-funded, administered by the UNHCR, supported by the Greek government, and implemented through collaboration between national and international non-governmental organizations as well as local municipalities.²⁸ The primary beneficiaries of ESTIA's accommodation provisions were vulnerable families, on average comprised of four members.

Half of the beneficiaries originated from Syria, with Iraqis and Afghans being the next most aided by this assistance.²⁹

The actors responsible for implementing the accommodation component also supported beneficiaries in acquiring essential documents (such as tax identification and social security numbers), opening bank accounts, and enrolling in schools.³⁰ Importantly, the urban locations of ESTIA-supported apartments facilitated social interactions with the Greek host population, thereby promoting the integration of migrant individuals and families into the host society.

While the coordination of ESTIA's urban housing scheme was overseen by UNHCR until late 2020, the responsibility for implementation shifted to the Greek state on 1 January 2021.³¹ Despite the guaranteed EU funding via AMIF until 2027, the Ministry of Migration and Asylum decreed in mid-2022 that the low numbers of asylum seekers in the country had rendered the ESTIA accommodation component redundant. Consequently, the Ministry of Migration and Asylum announced the program's discontinuation by late 2022, a decision met with disappointment and frustration from both beneficiaries and civil society organizations.³² Asylum-seekers were consequently directed to return to refugee camps if they wanted to continue receiving financial assistance.³³

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Although the housing component of ESTIA was terminated in late 2022, the program's second key element, which involves providing financial assistance to asylum seekers, is still ongoing. Cash assistance has been provided since 2017 through the Greece Cash Alliance, a coalition of NGOs working alongside and under the guidance of UNHCR.³⁴ The cash assistance pillar of ESTIA was initially funded by the AMIF Fund and conducted in collaboration with the Ministry of Migration and Asylum. After October 2021, however, UNHCR stopped providing this cash assistance in Greece, and the program is now administered instead by the Ministry of Migration and Asylum in collaboration with Catholic Relief Services (CRS).³⁵

Under the cash assistance program, asylum seekers are provided with prepaid cash cards, which are loaded monthly. They can either withdraw funds from ATMs or use the cards directly at point-of-sale (POS) terminals in stores. As a result, they are empowered to secure and prioritize their basic needs while also directly contributing to the host community's economy.³⁶

There is a cap on cash aid to ensure it does not exceed the national Guaranteed Minimum Income (GMI) value of cash transfers, and the amount of cash assistance is conditional on the number of family members and whether or not food is provided at the accommodation in which they reside.³⁷ Assistance varies from €75 for an individual in state-provided accommodations with meals to

€420 for a family of four or more residing in accommodations without meals.³⁸ As of June 2023, there are 5,000 beneficiaries of the cash assistance program.³⁹

ESTIA and its two components were aimed toward asylum seekers. Once the refugee status or subsidiary protection was granted, beneficiaries could then seek further assistance from the HELIOS (Hellenic Integration Support for Beneficiaries of International Protection and Temporary Protection) program.⁴⁰ HELIOS is implemented by the IOM, in collaboration with national authorities, NGOs, and municipalities. Until 31 December 2021, it was funded by the EU, while as of 1 January 2022, it is funded by the Ministry of Migration and Asylum.⁴¹

HELIOS is designed to assist recognized refugees and recipients of subsidiary protection in integrating into the host society and developing independence from welfare. Since 2018, when the program's implementation began, almost 45,000 individuals have benefited from HELIOS' provisions.⁴² Following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the subsequent displacement of Ukrainians across Europe, the program extended its scope in June 2022 to provide support for Ukrainian refugees in Greece.⁴³

IMPLEMENTING EU MIGRATION AND ASYLUM POLICIES AT THE SOUTHERN EUROPEAN BORDERS

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The Schengen Convention of 1995 further established the importance of safeguarding EU borders. Alongside creating a common visa policy, a framework to regulate the circulation of foreign nationals, and an information sharing system for security and border management called Schengen Information System (SIS), the Schengen Convention catalyzed two main consequences relevant to this article.⁴⁴ Its first was to abolish internal border checks for countries that signed the agreement.⁴⁵ As of late 2023, the Schengen Area contains a majority of EU countries, except for Bulgaria, Cyprus, Ireland, and Romania, as well as the non-EU States Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, and Liechtenstein. Therefore, individuals (including immigrants and refugees) who are already inside the Schengen Area would not be checked when moving from one country to another.

Abolishing EU internal border checks led to a second consequence: it became imperative to fortify and more effectively secure the Union's external borders. This logic placed a significant burden on the countries at the periphery of the Union, such as Greece, Italy, and Spain. From that point forward, border controls and their management constituted a principal concern of the Schengen Area, serving as a prerequisite for implementing an Area of Freedom, Security,

and Justice, as envisaged by the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. Consequently, the movement of migrants and refugees en masse across external EU borders from 2015-2016 (continued toward other EU Member States) placed the Schengen system under increased pressure. Starting from September 2015, several EU Member States opted to reinstate inspections at their internal borders, thereby reversing and calling into question the very survival of the Schengen Area.⁴⁶

To better manage the migration and refugee flows of this period, in May 2015, the EU unveiled the European Agenda on Immigration.⁴⁷ This Agenda introduced a strategy to tackle both the immediate and the persistent challenges of effectively managing migration flows. Furthermore, to address the root causes of instability, irregular migration, and forced displacement from Africa, the EU launched the Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF for Africa). A total of €5 billion has been earmarked for the implementation of the Fund, aiming to address challenges across the Sahel and Lake Chad, Horn of Africa, and North Africa regions.⁴⁸

Two more initiatives within the Agenda's framework were mechanisms targeting relocation and resettlement. Resettlement from Turkey occurred within the scope of the 2016 EU–Turkey Statement. Among others, the Statement aimed to discourage irregular and dangerous migration routes, while at the same time providing legal pathways for refugees in need of international protection. To this end, for every Syrian migrant returned from Greece to Turkey, one Syrian refugee from Turkey would be resettled in the EU. Under the Statement provisions, 2,735 people have been returned from Greece to Turkey, and over 32,000 Syrian refugees have been resettled from Turkey to EU Member States.⁴⁹

Additionally, acknowledging the stress that both Greece and Italy were facing in 2015 and seeking to promote solidarity and burden sharing, the EU's relocation initiative sought to relocate 160,000 asylum seekers to other European countries.⁵⁰ While only 33,154 were eventually relocated, the proposal sparked deep divisions between EU Member States, as the Visegrad Group—consisting of the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia—strongly refused to comply with the policy.⁵¹

Apart from these initiatives, another key component of the Agenda was the “hotspot approach,” which aimed to have EU agencies—European Asylum Support Office (EASO), Frontex, Europol, and Eurojust—work in tandem with national authorities at the external borders of the EU. In designated locations, called “hotspots,” these organizations would be in a position to swiftly identify, register, and fingerprint arriving migrants; streamline the screening

of refugees; and facilitate coordinated returns.⁵² According to this framework, the EU Agencies would operate complementarily: EASO would support teams expediting the processing of asylum cases and Frontex would coordinate the return of irregular migrants. Meanwhile, Europol and Eurojust would aid the host Member State in investigating smuggling and trafficking networks.⁵³ To this end, four “hotspots” were established in Italy and five in Greece (in the islands of Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Leros, and Kos).

Officially known as Reception and Identification Centres (RICs), hotspots in Greece commenced operations in late 2015, beginning with the center in Moria, Lesbos. By 2016, all remaining hotspots were fully operational. While initially conceived as registration facilities, following the EU-Turkey Statement, these hotspots trans-

Following the EU-Turkey Statement, these hotspots transformed into spaces of indefinite stay, essentially converting Greek islands into “prison islands.”

formed into spaces of indefinite stay, essentially converting Greek islands into “prison islands.”⁵⁴ In these spaces, newly arrived migrants remain until they are granted protection in Greece or are returned to Turkey based on the Statement provisions. Starting in 2021, new Closed Controlled Access Centres of Islands (CCACI), which are specifically designed from the outset and emphasize containment, restriction of movement, and surveillance, are gradually becoming operational and are substituting RICs on the islands.⁵⁵

One of the primary challenges in implementing the hotspot approach in Greece was the outsized ratio between designed capacity and actual occupancy. In September 2020, for instance, the total reception capacity of the hotspots was 6,095, yet their occupancy reached 23,269.⁵⁶ In certain hotspots, this discrepancy was even larger. Moria, the hotspot on Lesbos, had a capacity of 2,757 but hosted 12,767 individuals.⁵⁷ The situation was even more severe in Samos, where the hotspot was designed for 648 individuals, but housed 4,643.⁵⁸ The new CCACIs are projected to increase the overall capacity to 15,934 spaces.⁵⁹ However, a significant surge of migrant and refugee arrivals in autumn 2023 is already placing the new system under pressure; it is estimated that by mid-September 2023, more than 12,400 individuals were housed in the island’s reception facilities.⁶⁰

The overcrowding in all Greek hotspots raised security concerns and led to mounting pressure on infrastructure, medical services, and waste management. The living conditions were often characterized as substandard, while the situ-

ation in the new CCACI centers are described as “prison-like.”⁶¹ Indicatively, in order to enter and exit the camp, residents were required to pass through a series of security measures, including turnstiles, magnetic gates, x-ray screenings, and a two-factor access control system.⁶² These factors, coupled with gaps in access to asylum procedures and legal remedies, have caused significant tensions among the camp inhabitants. Migrants’ extended detention in hotspots has raised serious questions about their fundamental rights.⁶³ Meanwhile, the sense of hopelessness many have experienced during detention is associated with depression and mental health concerns.⁶⁴ In particular, the situation in Moria was described as an “unprecedented health and mental health emergency” by Médecins Sans Frontières.⁶⁵

The hotspot approach determined the “where” in implementing EU migration management at the borders. The “who” facilitating this strategy, apart from national authorities, mainly consisted of two European Agencies: Frontex and the European Union Agency for Asylum (EUAA). The EUAA, originally established in 2011 as the European Asylum Support Office (EASO), intended to assist EU Member States in implementing and harmonizing their asylum policies, particularly in cases of asylum pressure. The Agency proved instrumental in assisting Greece since 2015, providing vital operational support to process migrants’ applications as quickly as possible, inform asylum procedures and relocation, and match asylum-seekers with the appropriate Member State for relocation.⁶⁶

Frontex was established in 2004 and became operational during the 2006 crisis in the Canary Islands, Spain.⁶⁷ Working to enhance and coordinate border security efforts, Frontex played an important role in assisting Greece with managing refugee flows from Turkey. This aid extended to borders in the Aegean Sea and land borders in the Evros region. Additionally, it provided support in registration and identification procedures, as well as in coordinating the return of irregular migrants who were either denied asylum or did not have the right to remain in the EU.⁶⁸

However, while Frontex’s operation was instrumental in supporting the Greek efforts, at the same time its border control and surveillance initiatives, as well as its risk analysis and policy recommendations, are regarded as significantly responsible for the framing of migration as a security threat in the EU.⁶⁹ Additionally, there has been emerging evidence indicating that Frontex was aware of pushback operations conducted by Greek authorities and may have been involved in efforts to conceal them. An investigation carried out by the European Anti-Fraud Office identified these practices, while its release to the

general public is possibly linked to the resignation of the Frontex Director in April 2022.⁷⁰

Despite these developments, there remained an urgent need for an agency that would enhance operational cooperation at the EU's external borders. Consequently, Frontex was restructured in 2016, transforming into the European Border and Coast Guard Agency.⁷¹ The new Agency now holds the authority to directly intervene if a Member State faces challenges in controlling its borders. This may include the authorization of rapid border interventions or the coordination of joint operations.⁷² Moreover, plans are underway to establish a European Border and Coast Guard Standing Corps, projected to comprise up to 10,000 operational staff by 2027.⁷³ These corps will be deployed along the external land, sea, and air borders of the European Union and the Schengen Area. To implement this broadened mandate, Frontex's budget has seen a significant increase from €143 million in 2015 to €754 million in 2022.⁷⁴

Finally, as briefly mentioned earlier in relation to Frontex, another key point regarding border management in Greece concerns allegations of “pushback operations.” Pushback practices demonstrate a denial of a State's international obligation to protect the human rights of migrants and asylum seekers at international borders, and result in human rights violations on the prohibition of collective expulsion and refoulement. They are defined as:

Various measures taken by States, sometimes involving third countries or non-State actors, which result in migrants, including asylum seekers, being summarily forced back, without an individual assessment of their human rights protection needs, to the country or territory, or to sea, whether it be territorial waters or international waters, from where they attempted to cross or crossed an international border.⁷⁵

Accusations of pushback operations in Greece have been documented since at least the late 2000s.⁷⁶ However, their frequency has notably surged since 2016, particularly in the Evros region. The Greek Ombudsman, an independent authority overseeing citizens' rights and administrative fairness, has identified standardized procedures in pushback operations. During these operations, intercepted individuals have their phones and IDs confiscated by the police, are handed over to unidentified individuals, taken to undisclosed buildings, and within 24 hours forced onto dinghies and transported to the Turkish bank of the Evros River. These operations, therefore, appear to involve state agencies and state agents at the levels of operational planning, logistics, and perpetrators.⁷⁷

The official government position is that “[a]llegations affecting Greece are clearly unfounded ... [n]umerous cases have been investigated, including by

the European Union and reports have found no evidence of any breach of EU fundamental rights.”⁷⁸ However, the UN Special Rapporteur on the Human Rights of Migrants elevated their policy significance, arguing that “[i]n Greece, pushbacks at land and sea borders have become de facto general policy.” The Special Rapporteur further argued that “Greece reportedly deterred over 140,000 people from entering the country between April and November 2021.”⁷⁹

Within this context, the June 2023 shipwreck in Pylos has raised questions regarding the role of the Greek authorities and the Coast Guard. This comes in the wake of media reports that provided insight into how the incident occurred and was managed.⁸⁰ The shipwreck prompted Frontex to initiate a “Serious Incident Report” to gather the fatal incident’s details, while the Agency’s Fundamental Rights Officer recommended a temporary suspension of its activity in Greece.⁸¹

RESPONDING TO THE WEAPONIZATION OF MIGRANTS AND REFUGEES

The signing and implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement resulted in a noteworthy reduction in the number of irregular crossings from Turkey to Greece, especially in the years soon after the agreement went into effect. However, this movement never came to a complete halt. 50,500 sea and land arrivals were recorded in 2018 and 75,000 in 2019.⁸²

A dramatic escalation regarding the situation at the Greek-Turkish land borders occurred in February–March 2020, as Turkey actively encouraged migrants and refugees to force their way through Greece to continue their journey to Europe.⁸³ According to official Turkish statements, the EU had violated the EU-Turkey Statement by delaying funds distribution. Within this agreement, the EU pledged €6 billion to aid refugees in Turkey to be administered through the EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey.⁸⁴ Turkish President Erdogan stated in response to this perceived violation:

We said months ago that if it goes on like this, we will have to open the doors. They did not believe us, but we opened the doors yesterday... We will not close these doors in the coming period and this will continue. Why? The European Union needs to keep its promises. We don't have to take care of this many refugees, to feed them.⁸⁵

This call resulted in the movement of 12,000–25,000 people to the Turkish side of the Greek borders in the Kastanies-Pazarkule area.⁸⁶ In the following days, a series of violent clashes took place at the land borders of the Evros region,

as immigrants continuously attempted to cross the border points of Kipoi and Kastanies. The Greek army, reinforced by riot police units, largely prevented the borders from being overrun.⁸⁷

The EU promptly responded to this development through a combination of tangible measures and symbolic gestures. A joint visit to the Greek border by the Presidents of the European Parliament, the European Council, and the European Commission on 3 March 2023, while immigrants were still attempting to force their way into Greece, produced strong statements and made explicit EU's support to Greece.⁸⁸ As publicly expressed by the Vice-President for Promoting our European Way of Life, "We have to show unequivocally that the entire European Union will put its strength and support behind Member States faced with external pressure."⁸⁹ At the same time, the Council of the EU underlined that:

The EU and its Member States remain determined to effectively protect EU's external borders. Illegal crossings will not be tolerated. In this regard, the EU and its Member States will take all necessary measures... The Council calls upon the Turkish government and all actors and organizations on the ground to relay this message.⁹⁰

In addition to the above statements, the EU sanctioned an Action Plan to further support Greece in managing the situation. The plan included launching two rapid border intervention operations by Frontex, deploying 160 experts by EASO, and providing financial assistance of up to €700 million.⁹¹

The above initiatives reveal a stark contrast between how the EU perceived Greece's management of migration, asylum, and border controls during the Evros crisis and how they viewed it in the past. Before 2015, Greece was often condemned by EU

institutions for its treatment of asylum seekers or the overall systematic deficiencies of its asylum system.⁹² In the early 2010s, Greece was also accused of insufficiently guarding the EU's external

borders since it accounted for 90 percent of all detections of irregular border crossings along all EU external land and sea borders.⁹³ However, by the time of the Evros crisis, both the presence of top EU officials in the borders area

Both the presence of top EU officials in the borders area as well as the official EU discourse made it explicit that Greece was, first and foremost, a protector of EU borders.

as well as the official EU discourse made it explicit that Greece was, first and foremost, a protector of EU borders. As the European Commission president, Ursula von der Leyen, stated during her visit: “This border is not only a Greek border, it is also a European border ... I thank Greece for being our European *aspida* [shield] in these times.”⁹⁴

The Evros crisis triggered a heated domestic public debate centered around themes of security, asymmetric threats, and the human rights of immigrants and refugees.⁹⁵ These were especially pronounced when the Greek government passed on 2 March 2020, an urgent legislative act that temporarily suspended asylum applications from people who illegally arrived in the country.⁹⁶

The Evros crisis undeniably had immigration policy concerns, and more precisely, border management issues, at its core. Yet, a more nuanced reading of the situation should also perceive the incident not only in terms of migration policy but also in terms of foreign policy. Under this perspective, Turkey instrumentalized immigrants to pursue its foreign policy objectives, placing pressure on both Greece and the EU. As far as Greece is concerned, this can be seen as part of a broader culmination and significant escalation of Turkey’s provocative actions witnessed in the previous months.⁹⁷

14 Regarding Turkey’s EU pressure campaign, Turkish President Erdogan clearly stated that opening Turkey’s borders was a consequence of late EU payments related to the EU-Turkey Statement. However, the timing of the incident also coincided with the death of more than 30 Turkish soldiers in Idlib, Syria, during a Syrian regime offensive.⁹⁸ As such, it is possible that Turkey used a calculated gambit in Greece, albeit unsuccessfully, to gain support from the EU regarding the situation in Syria.

One of the key lessons from that incident was that the EU made clear it would not tolerate the “use of migratory pressure for political purposes.”⁹⁹ Nevertheless, a similar scenario played again a few months later, with the government of Belarus weaponizing migrants to support state policy.¹⁰⁰ In response to repeated rounds of EU sanctions, Belarusian President Aleksandr Lukashenko declared that the country would no longer prevent illegal immigration into the EU. Notably, Belarussian authorities facilitated the transfer of Kurds from Iraq and Syria into Belarus by issuing special visas, then directed them toward the borders shared with Latvia, Lithuania, and Poland.¹⁰¹ This movement prompted Lithuanian Interior Minister Agne Bilotaite to label the increased migration as a form of “hybrid warfare,” while European Commission spokesman Adalbert Jahnz argued that “The situation at the Polish-Belarussian border constitutes an act of aggression towards Poland.”¹⁰²

CRITICALLY EVALUATING THE POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Through an in-depth analysis of Greek and European policies and responses at the European borders over the past decade, this article aims to highlight three areas of importance.

The first area concerns refugees' integration. With substantial support from UNHCR and other organizations, as well as generous financial contributions from the EU, Greece has successfully established a functioning humanitarian assistance mechanism in the form of ESTIA. This program has effectively addressed the immediate needs of asylum seekers, while HELIOS offers time-limited support for recognized refugees.

However, when we consider the long-term prospects for integrating these populations, the situation does not appear promising. Ending ESTIA's urban accommodation scheme and redirecting all asylum seekers to camps promotes a logic of warehousing and significantly hinders the integration potential of this population. Regarding refugee accommodations, between 2018 and 2020, HELIOS provided support to only one out of seven recognized refugees.¹⁰³ Additionally, artificial barriers have been put in place by Greece which obstruct the transition of refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection from humanitarian assistance to the welfare state, hinting at discrimination.¹⁰⁴ Finally, the theme of integration is notably absent from the Ministry of Migration and Asylum 2023 Action Plan.¹⁰⁵ These factors strongly suggest that the integration of this population is, at best, an afterthought in Greece's official immigration and asylum policy.

Secondly, Greece faces a balancing act in its attempt to address migration-related security concerns while striving to uphold humanitarian obligations. As previously mentioned, Greece had been struggling for decades to meet its humanitarian commitments. The 2011 asylum system reforms, along with significant EU financial assistance and the support provided by the EUAA, have all contributed to a more functional asylum system. However, security concerns continue to hold a prominent position on the agenda since migration has become characterized as a security threat in Greece both before and after 2015.¹⁰⁶

Furthermore, this paper has signaled how migrants are viewed and labeled as threats, evident in the events of Evros in 2020 and indirectly in Greece's pushback incidents. According to the official discourse, Greece's "tough but fair" migration policy has placed immigration "under control."¹⁰⁷ The expansion of the border fence in Evros, which coincided with the 2023 national elections,

also contributed to this narrative.¹⁰⁸ However, the sharp increase of inflows in both Greece and Italy in 2023 undermine this notion and raise doubts about the extent to which security-driven approaches alone are sufficient to manage the phenomenon properly.

The final remark has to do with the EU and EU Member States' approach toward migration and crisis management. While the 2015 crisis was initially understood as being about the absolute number of refugees entering the EU, it gradually evolved into a crisis of politics, policies, and institutions.¹⁰⁹ This crisis manifested in several ways, but most importantly, as one regarding the meaning of solidarity.¹¹⁰ Italy and Greece interpreted solidarity in terms of burden sharing, and therefore requested refugee relocation. On the other hand, some Member States interpreted solidarity as providing technical and financial support. Even more so, other Member States proved reluctant to display any form of solidarity. This ambiguity on the interpretation of EU terms such as "solidarity," is a key characteristic of EU asylum policy.¹¹¹ However, we have now reached the point where, according to the EU's external affairs commissioner, "migration is a bigger divide for the European Union, and it could be a dissolving force for the European Union."¹¹²

To this end, the European Commission introduced in 2020 the New Pact on Migration and Asylum. Its aim is to overhaul the EU's approach to migration and asylum policies by replacing the earlier Dublin Regulation and addressing the challenges faced by EU member states in managing migration flows. Overall it attempts to balance the previously mentioned diverging approaches and interpretations in an effort to move the EU Migration and Asylum Policy forward. Greece, situated at the borders of the EU, will yet again play a key role in these developments.

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